

The Indian Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC) – 1973 Under Section 293: Reports of Some Government Scientific Experts

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SUMMARY

Mahatma Gandhi's famous quote "Justice that love gives is surrender; justice that law gives is a punishment". Report is which technical essential ingredients it must have the nomenclature of different types of government reports. We shall hereafter take up the content of the report, how it should be developed systematically so that it becomes acceptable to the management. A report is a scientific statement of facts and figure can be oral report or written government report. It can also be a simple or routine report or a complex report. Reports play a very important role for government organization and government authority. Reports are generally written by an individual or a group of persons committee after they have studied something related problem. The broad objectives and aim of any report should therefore be narrating what has been observed, a threadbare analysis of the observations and conclusions arising out of such analysis. A report is then submitted for the consideration of the government and court higher authorities, their decision and action. Thus a report is an upward communication for decision on problem.

INTRODUCTION

In India, Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC) is the main legislation on code procedure for administration of substantive criminal law. This act is passed in India on date 25 January 1973. Under this act, crime investigation, collection of evidence, prevention of offences and punishment related processes are done. In India, all government legislation system followed this Code procedure. Currently, this act contains 484 sections, schedules and 56 forms. The sections are divided into 37 chapters.

Section 293 in the Code of Criminal Procedure (1973) Reports of Some Government Scientific Experts

1. Any document purporting to be a report under the hand of a Government scientific expert to whom this section applies, upon any matter or thing duly submitted to him for examination or analysis and report in the course of any proceeding under this code may be used as evidence in any inquiry, trial or other proceeding under this Code.
2. The Court may, if it thinks fit, summon and examine any such expert as to the subject- matter of his report.
3. Where any such expert is summoned by a Court and he is unable to attend personally, he may, unless the Court has expressly directed him to appear personally, depute any responsible officer working with him to attend the Court, if such officer is conversant with the facts of the case and can satisfactorily depose in Court on his behalf.
4. This section applies to the following Government scientific experts, namely:
 - Any Chemical Examiner or Assistant Chemical Examiner to Government
 - The Chief Inspector of- Explosives
 - The Director of the Finger Print Bureau
 - The Director, Haffkeine Institute, Bombay

- The Director, Deputy Director or Assistant Director of a Central Forensic Science Laboratory or a State Forensic Science Laboratory
- The Serologist to the Government

A Mode of Taking and Recording Evidence

Under law of Evidence act 1872, Government reports scientific writing means is technical expert reports issued by any Governmental Department Authority with Effect. A report is looked upon in high value as it is either prepared document by a technical expert in the any field or after thorough study filed of the matter in great detail. Therefore, it is natural that the report has at least the following ingredients:

- A Report should be logical, sequential and honest – it should not only be fair but should establish that fairness has been observed throughout the process of enquiry and report
- It should be factual, supported by figures and documents Technical Report
- It should be cogent, clear and accurate facts and figure
- It should be brief explain, look small and have a catchy title of report
- It should be coherent. Different sections add of the Report should cleared appear to be leading from one to another section
- It should have proper linking document and references for the material used and included other document
- No personal opinions technical opinion should be included, nor should there be any loose statement
- The recommendations should not be utopian those should be practicable and implementable
- The report should not deviate from the given mandate
- It must have a specific scientific format
- It should appear to be aimed at people with a specific interest in the area covered by the report

The points following can be represent identification:

a) Cover Page: This happens to be first thing that attracts the attention of the Reader. As such it has to be attractive and appealing. It should normally contain the title of the report, Name of the Organization, Composition of the Team and the date of submission of the Report.

b) Title: Title should be short – not more than 5-6 words. It should be catchy and not a narrative sentence. However, it should represent the contents completely and clearly. In order to make it catchy, gimmickry of words and phrases should not be resorted to. For example, a report on misappropriation of funds should state as such and not “Robbing Peter to pay Paul”.

c) Forwarding Letter: This is a communication from the team along with which the Report is formally submitted to the authority that entrusted the work of preparing it.

d) Authority: This refers to the authorization to prepare the report. It should be referred to in the forwarding letter and a copy of the communication giving the mandate should form part of the Annexure.

e) Table of Contents: In case the report is of a routine nature and is short (not exceeding 5-6 pages), no table of contents would be necessary. However, for longer reports a „Table of Contents“ indicating all items, including Appendices and Annexure, etc. along with page numbers needs to be added to guide the reader.

f) Glossary of Terms: If some words peculiar to the subject under study or the organization have been used, it would be useful to include a “Glossary of Terms” to facilitate understanding.

g) Bibliography: It’s a list of references, sources from where substantial material has been drawn into the report. This can be done by means of footnotes at the appropriate places or in a separate section in the report with respect to the compliance or non-compliance of any Company Party with applicable Laws.

Types of Reports

Types of Reports	
Routine	Special
Progress Report or	Investigation Report
Inspection Report	Feasibility Report
Performance Appraisal report	Survey Report
Periodical Reports	Project Report
Daily Action Report	Inquest Report or Panchnama
Daily Diary Annual Report	incident Report or Accident Report
Technical Reports	Action Taken Report

Pointers to score high in Report Writing

- Use Proper names and pronouns in report
- Limit yourself to one idea per sentence as per requirement topics
- Clear and specific as possible subject discussion.
- Use simple language in drafting.
- Observable facts and figures.
- Write in paragraphs in technical report
- Use active voice in report.
- Use bullet style and figure

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, method for report writing and data collection or data interpretation is very important in criminal procedure code 1973. This information is useful for future study as well as for providing authenticity to the process of study. Reports should be in systematic way that it should be accepted by the government and the court. So overall good report writing skill is the key to evidences used in the court justice.

REFERENCES

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